

obtained by growing the fungus in Czapek's pectin broth were treated with different concentrations of the fungicide (0, 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1%) and assayed for production of protopectinase, polygalacturonase, polygalacturonate *trans* eliminase, and pectin *trans* eliminase. The activity of the enzymes cellulase (C₁), cellulase

(C_x), and β -glucosidase also were estimated.

Production of protopectinase, polygalacturonase, polygalacturonate *trans* eliminase, and pectin *trans* eliminase by *R. solani* was markedly inhibited in all concentrations of carbendazim (see table). Highest reduction was in 0.1% concentration.

Activity of cellulase (C₁) and cellulase (C_x) also was markedly inhibited. Highest inhibition of cellulase (C₁) and cellulase (C_x) activities was in 0.1% concentration.

Increases in carbendazim concentrations increased β -glucosidase activity. The increase was highest in 0.1% concentration. □

Influence of carbendazim concentrations on in vitro production of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes by *R. solani*.

Fungicide concentration (%)	Proto pectinase production ^a	Poly galacturonase production ^b	Poly galacturonate <i>trans</i> eliminase production ^c	Pectin <i>trans</i> eliminase production ^d	Cellulase activity units (C ₁)	Cellulase activity units (C _x) ^e	β -glucosidase ^f activity
0 (control)	++++	48.50	34.4	22.3	3.500	41.10	3.000
0.01	+++	32.60	24.7	17.1	2.350	30.33	3.532
0.05	++	28.50	18.8	13.4	1.797	25.54	4.246
0.1	+	8.10	8.5	6.4	0.812	13.22	4.925

^a Maceration of potato disc, + to ++++ = increase in activity. ^b Percent loss in viscosity of 0.75% sodium polypectate after 120 min. ^c Percent loss in viscosity of 1.2% sodium polypectate after 120 min. ^d Percent loss in viscosity of 1% citrus pectin after 120 min. ^e Percent loss in viscosity of 0.5% carboxy methyl cellulose after 120 min. ^f mg of reducing sugars liberated from 1% arbutin/100 ml.

Evaluating fungicides to control rice leaf scald (LSc) in the field

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We tested five fungicides against LSc *Gerlachia oryzae* Has. and Yokogi under field conditions 1987-88.

Rice cultivar Lalat was planted in 4 × 5-m plot at 15 × 20-cm spacing in a randomized block design with three replications. Plants were artificially inoculated during the evening 25 d after transplanting (DT) with a suspen-

sion of 30,000 spores/ml, using a plastic atomizer.

Seed treatment involved soaking seeds in carbendazim + thiram suspension for 12 h before sowing. Fungicides were sprayed at 30, 40, and 50 DT. Disease incidence was measured 55 DT.

Seed treatment with carbendazim + thiram was effective. Among spray treatments, thiophanate-methyl was most effective in reducing disease (see table). Carbendazim and maneb also significantly reduced disease. No phytotoxicity occurred in any treatment. □

Tungro (RTV) incidence in wetbed seedling nursery

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Rice farmers often raise nurseries in areas adjacent to the fields. Unprotected nurseries are suspected to play an important role in the spread of RTV.

We studied RTV incidence on rice seedlings in an unprotected wetbed nursery. Pregerminated TN1 seeds were sown in a 2 × 10-m nursery laid out in the middle of a field planted to TN1 with high RTV incidence.

At 21 d after seeding (DM), green leafhopper (GLH) in the nursery and in the plants surrounding the nursery were sampled by 10 sweeps of an insect net. GLH infectivity was tested by introducing one captured vector into a test tube containing a TN1 seedling for 24-h inoculation. Seedlings were indexed for RTV by ELISA 3 wk later.

At 21 DAS, seedlings in the field nursery were pulled and apportioned to cover four 7.5 × 8-m plots in the insect-proof screenhouse and four 5.5 × 9-m plots in the field. Two to three

Control of rice LSc disease by fungicides. Bhubaneswar, India, 1987-88.

Treatment	Application rate (kg/ha)	Disease incidence ^a (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
		1987	1988	1987	1988
Carbendazim + thiram (1:1) ^b	0.035 + 0.105	25.00 (28.31)	28.80 (32.45)	2.5	2.4
Carbendazim	0.8	16.80 (24.19)	27.20 (31.43)	2.8	2.5
Thiophanate-methyl	0.8	11.07 (19.43)	19.60 (26.27)	2.9	2.9
Maneb	1.0	23.20 (28.79)	27.90 (31.88)	2.7	2.4
Blitox	1.0	27.40 (31.56)	29.90 (33.14)	2.6	2.3
Control (unsprayed)		41.93 (40.35)	46.10 (42.76)	2.2	1.8
LSD (0.05)		2.4	2.28	0.3	0.3
(0.01)		3.41	3.24	0.4	0.3

^a Figures in parentheses are the transformed angular values. ^b Chemicals used as seed treatment.